

PROPHET: PReference-based OPTimization for Human-cEnTric visual inspection

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Abstract—The aim of this project (PROPHET) is to develop a visual inspection system able to automatically configure the control parameters, learning from the choices made by an expert operator. The resulting system will allow the adoption of automated visual inspection even in complex inspection tasks and reduce the setting up time by learning from skilled operators inspection results based also on their experience. The developed system will be tested in the inspection of 3 parts from different sectors (e.g., automotive and aerospace industry), evaluating its performance in comparison with manual and robotized inspections.

Index Terms—Human-centric production, human-robot collaboration, human-robot interaction, knowledge transfer, preference-based optimization, artificial intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics is increasingly devoted to assist humans in many different fields (such as rehabilitation, rescue, medical applications, etc.) [1]–[3]. A robotic system, therefore, has to enable and facilitate the task that the human has to execute, exploiting intelligent tools to capture the human’s needs, requirements, instructions, feedback, and satisfaction [4]. One of the most important application areas is represented by industrial workplaces [5]. Industry 4.0 [6] is evolving to Industry 5.0 [7] by improving the working conditions of the industrial operators alongside making use of human knowledge, adaptability, and intelligence. One of the main objectives of this new industrial revolution is to move the attention from connected cyber-physical systems to operators, designing human-centric production environments exploiting the human knowledge to improve the industrial processes [8]. The human is placed in the center of the production environment, playing a leading role instead of carrying out manual (heavy/repetitive) tasks. In fact, the human should be involved in high-added-value operations (*i.e.*, all the operations in which the expertise of the human can be exploited to improve the production process), instead of performing easily automatable tasks [9]. Thus, to fully exploit the expertise of the operators, tools to naturally and easily transfer such knowledge to robotic systems are required.

The main contribution of this project (PROPHET) is, therefore, to propose and validate a human-centric approach to transfer the human’s knowledge of a task into the robotic system, making use of qualitative feedback only. To this aim, preference-based optimization (PBO) is employed. In such

a way, non-expert programmers will be allowed to transfer their knowledge to robotic systems for the tuning of a target task. A visual inspection task is considered within the project. Indeed, a system able to automatically configure the control parameters, learning from the choices made by an expert operator, has to be developed. The resulting system will allow the adoption of automated visual inspection even in complex inspection tasks, reducing the setting up time by learning from skilled operators inspection results based also on their experience.

II. PREFERENCE-BASED OPTIMIZATION

The preference based optimization algorithm employed in this work is based on the methodology developed in [10] by some of the authors, where the GLISp (Global optimization based on active preference learning) algorithm is introduced.

A. Building a surrogate function from preferences

The first step of the GLISp (Global optimization based on active preference learning) algorithm is to build a surrogate function describing the observed preferences.

Formally, given two possible sets of parameters θ_1 and θ_2 , the *preference function* $\pi: \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \rightarrow \{-1, 0, 1\}$ is defined as:

$$\pi(\theta_1, \theta_2) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } \theta_1 \text{ "better" than } \theta_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \theta_1 \text{ "as good as" } \theta_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } \theta_2 \text{ "better" than } \theta_1. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Assuming that $N \geq 2$ samples $\{\theta_1 \dots \theta_N\}$ of the decision vector are generated, with $\theta_i, \theta_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ such that $\theta_i \neq \theta_j$, $\forall i \neq j$, with $i, j = 1, \dots, N$. For each of these parameters, an experiment is performed and the user provides a *preference vector* $\mathbf{B} = [b_1 \dots b_M]^T \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^M$ with:

$$b_h = \pi(\theta_{i(h)}, \theta_{j(h)}), \quad (2)$$

where M is the number of expressed preferences, $h \in \{1, \dots, M\}$, $i(h), j(h) \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, and $i(h) \neq j(h)$. It has to be noted that the element b_h of vector the \mathbf{B} represents the preference expressed by the user between the experimental performance achieved with the parameters $\theta_{i(h)}$ and $\theta_{j(h)}$.

The observed preferences are then used to learn a surrogate function $\hat{f}: \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of an (unknown) underlying performance

index J . The surrogate \hat{J} is parametrized as the following linear combination of Radial Basis Functions (RBFs):

$$\hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \beta_k \phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k)), \quad (3)$$

where $d: \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the squared Euclidean distance:

$$d(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_i) = \|\boldsymbol{\theta} - \boldsymbol{\theta}_i\|_2^2, \quad (4)$$

$\gamma > 0$ is a scalar parameter, $\phi: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an RBF, and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\beta_1 \dots \beta_N]^T$ are the unknown coefficients to be computed based on the available user's preferences. Examples of RBFs are $\phi(\gamma d) = \frac{1}{1+(\gamma d)^2}$ (*inverse quadratic*) and $\phi(\gamma d) = e^{-(\gamma d)^2}$ (*Gaussian*) (see [10] for more details).

According to the preference relation (1), the surrogate \hat{J} has to satisfy the following constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}) &\leq \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}) - \sigma + \varepsilon_h & \text{if } \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}) = -1 \\ \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}) &\geq \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}) + \sigma - \varepsilon_h & \text{if } \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}) = 1 \\ |\hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}) - \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)})| &\leq \sigma + \varepsilon_h & \text{if } \pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

for all $h = 1, \dots, M$, where $\sigma > 0$ is a given tolerance and ε_h is a positive slack variable which is used to relax the preference constraints. Constraints infeasibility might be due to an inappropriate selection of the RBF (namely, poor flexibility in the parametric description of the surrogate \hat{J}) and/or inconsistent assessments done by the user.

Based on the above preference constraints, the coefficient vector $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ describing the surrogate \hat{J} is obtained by solving the Quadratic Programming (QP) problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\boldsymbol{\beta}, \varepsilon} \quad & \sum_{h=1}^M \varepsilon_h + \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N \beta_k^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{k=1}^N (\phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k)) - \phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k))) \beta_k \\ & \leq -\sigma + \varepsilon_h, \quad \forall h: b_h = -1 \\ & \sum_{k=1}^N (\phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k)) - \phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k))) \beta_k \\ & \geq \sigma - \varepsilon_h, \quad \forall h: b_h = 1 \\ & \left| \sum_{k=1}^N (\phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{i(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k)) - \phi(\gamma d(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{j(h)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_k))) \beta_k \right| \\ & \leq \sigma + \varepsilon_h, \quad \forall h: b_h = 0 \\ & h = 1, \dots, M. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The scalar $\lambda > 0$ in the cost function (6) is a regularization parameter which guarantees uniqueness in the solution of the QP problem.

B. Acquisition function

Once a surrogate \hat{J} is estimated, this function can be minimized in order to find the optimal parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

More in detail, the following steps can be followed:

(i) generate a new sample by pure minimization of the estimated surrogate function \hat{J} , *i.e.*,

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{N+1} = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad \text{s.t. } \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta;$$

- (ii) ask the user to express a preference $\pi(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{N+1}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N^*)$, where $\boldsymbol{\theta}_N^* \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ is the vector of parameters with the best experimental output (judged by the user) found so far;
- (iii) update the estimate of \hat{J} through (6);
- (iv) iterate over N .

Such a procedure, which only *exploits* the current available observations in finding the optimal parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, may easily miss a more performing set of parameters. Indeed, a term promoting the *exploration* of the parameter space should be considered.

In the GLISp algorithm, an acquisition function is employed to balance exploitation *vs.* exploration when generating the new sample $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{N+1}$. The exploration function is defined by using the inverse distance weighting (IDW) function $z: \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as:

$$z(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N\} \\ \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i(\boldsymbol{\theta})} \right) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $w_i(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{d^2(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\theta}_i)}$. Clearly, $z(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = 0$ for all parameters already tested, and $z(\boldsymbol{\theta}) > 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \setminus \{\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N\}$. The arc tangent function in (7) avoids that $z(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ gets excessively large far away from all sampled points.

Then, given an exploration parameter $\delta \geq 0$, the *acquisition function* $a: \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is constructed as:

$$a(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{\hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\Delta \hat{J}} - \delta z(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (8)$$

where

$$\Delta \hat{J} = \max_i \{\hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i)\} - \min_i \{\hat{J}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i)\}$$

is the range of the surrogate function on the samples in $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N\}$ and used in (8) as a normalization factor to simplify the choice of the exploration parameter δ .

Given a set $\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_N\}$ of samples and a vector \mathbf{B} of preferences defined in (2), the next parameter set $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{N+1}$ to be tested is computed as the solution of the (non-convex) optimization problem:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{N+1} = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta} a(\boldsymbol{\theta}). \quad (9)$$

III. USE CASE

The approach developed in this project will be tested in the visual inspection of complex parts such as an engine.

Currently, at the end of the assembly process, the engine is inspected for approval by a skilled operator through visual inspection. Operator perform the inspection of different characteristics of its assembly such as presence of screws, proper tubes' path, or correct seating of electrical plugs. Figure 1 shows some of the inspection task that will be done on the engine.

Automate the visual inspection of the engine requires the configuration of different inspection check: presence/absence; alignment (spatial orientation of a component respect a notch, another component or the vertical of the motor); compliance

Fig. 1. Visual inspection task.

(the component mounted it's the corrected one). Each component to be verified requires a fine tuning of multiple parameters (e.g. tollerances). To this end, the transfert of the experience of the operator is mandatory, but it is complex in if the operator have no experience in programming and requires in most cases a trials and error approach to reach the goal.

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